

Theory on modified Newton's second law and law of gravity based on statistical mechanics

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Abstract: Inspired by the entropy of black holes, two-dimensional sphere is regarded as an interacting particle system, this paper uses the method of canonical ensemble to get the modified Newton's second law and law of gravity, and it shows that Modified Newtonian Dynamics (MOND) may be an approximate form of the modified Newton's second law. It is found that modified Newton's second law can explain the Dirac's large numbers hypothesis and it shows that the gravitational constant increases extremely slowly over time. By fitting high-precision measurements of the gravitational constant over the past two decades, result shows that our theory agrees very well with the experimental data of different experimental groups.

Keywords: modified Newton's second law; MOND; large numbers hypothesis; gravitational constant.

1. Introduction

In 1687, Newton proposed the law of universal gravitation and Newton's second law in the *Philosophiae Naturalis Principia Mathematica*. However, why is force simply proportional to acceleration? What is the nature of gravity? What is the propagation speed of gravity? Newton's theory cannot answer these questions. In 1915, Einstein proposed the general relativity, and he explained gravity as the curvature of time and space. In 2010, Verlinde put forward a novel point of view, and he believed that gravity is a kind of entropy force. He also derived Newton's second law and General Relativity under his assumption¹.

In 1970, Vera Rubin discovered that the speed of stars and gas clouds outside the Andromeda galaxy M31 are much faster than expected, and the galaxy's rotation curve is strangely flat on the outside². Roberts and Rots believed that spiral galaxies may have a bit more mass than normal optical measurements suggest, they thought that there is a large invisible matter halo outside the galaxy³. Milgrom believed that the rotation curve of galaxies can be explained by Modified Newtonian dynamics (MOND), which shows the relationship between force and acceleration is no longer linear when the gravitational field is very weak⁴.

In 1973, Dirac proposed a "Large Number Hypothesis". He believed that gravitation constant G varies with time by studying the relations between two large dimensionless numbers⁵, scalar-tensor gravity theory believes that the gravitational constant is determined by the reciprocal of the average value of a scalar field⁶. In addition, some experiments show that the gravitational constant varies with the distance⁷.

In the law of universal gravitation, the gravitational constant G is a universal constant and is not affected by the size, shape, composition and other factors of the object. In 1798, the British physicist Cavendish used the Cavendish torsion pendulum made by Michell to accurately measure the density of

the earth for the first time, the first G value ($6.6754 \times 10^{-11} \text{ m}^3 \text{ kg}^{-1} \text{ s}^{-2}$) was derived based on his experimental results⁸. So far, different research groups in the world have measured the gravitational constant, however, some measurement results of different experimental groups are inconsistent within the error range⁹. The phenomenon has not been well explained at present.

Herein, method of statistical physics is used to derive the law of gravity and modified Newton's second law. It shows that the temperature change of the vacuum leads to the generation of gravity. By comparing Modified Newtonian Dynamics with modified Newton's second law, the first two terms of the Taylor expansion of the modified Newton's second law are consistent with Modified Newtonian Dynamics. Besides, the modified Newton's second law can be used to explain Dirac's "Large Number Hypothesis" and the inconsistency of the measurement results of the gravitational constant G .

2. Modified Newton's second law and law of gravity

2.1 Hypothesis: treat two-dimensional sphere as an interacting particle system

Bekenstein and Hawking believes that black hole has entropy proportional to its area¹⁰:

$$S = k \frac{A}{4\left(\frac{G\hbar}{c^3}\right)} \quad (1)$$

In this equation, S stands for the entropy of black hole, A is the event horizon area of black hole. If two-dimensional space is treated as an interacting particle system, and the size of space $4G\hbar/c^3$ is treated as the average size of the space occupied by a particle, the number of particles in a two-dimensional sphere with area A is:

$$N = \frac{A}{4\left(\frac{G\hbar}{c^3}\right)} \quad (2)$$

If average number of states of each particle in gravitational field is the natural constant e , the total number of states of two-dimensional space with area A is:

$$\Omega = e^N \quad (3)$$

The equation of Boltzmann entropy is:

$$S = k \ln \Omega \quad (4)$$

Under this hypothesis, it is easy to get equation (1) according to equation (3) and equation (4). It seems to imply that the two-dimensional sphere can be treated as an interacting particle system.

N vibrations with interaction can be transformed into 2N near-independent simple harmonic vibrations¹¹. The energy of 2N near-independent simple harmonic vibrations is:

$$E = \varphi_0 + \sum_{i=1}^{2N} \hbar \omega_i \left(n_i + \frac{1}{2} \right), \quad n_i = 0, 1, 2 \dots \dots \quad (5)$$

When De Broglie standing wave condition is applied in the observable universe, angular frequency in the equation satisfies the following relation:

$$2\pi R = n_j \frac{2\pi c}{\omega_j}, \quad n_j = 1, 2, 3 \dots \dots \quad (6)$$

Here, R is the radius of the observable universe. According to equation (6) and equation (5), the following equation is obtained:

$$E = \varphi_0 + \sum_{j=1}^{2N} \hbar \omega'_0 \left(\frac{1+n_k}{2} \right) \quad n_k = 0, 1, 2 \dots \dots \quad (7)$$

Here ω'_0 of this equation is the minimum angular frequency of a wave in our universe.

$$\omega'_0 = \frac{c}{R} \quad (8)$$

And then the partition function Z of the particle system can be figured out based on statistical mechanics.

2.2 Modified Newton's second law and Gravity

If there is a body in space, the body will produce a gravitational field. According to the Unruh effect¹²:

$$kT = \frac{\hbar a}{2\pi c} \quad (9)$$

The acceleration will cause the vacuum to produce thermal radiation. A two-dimensional sphere centered on this object would be exposed to thermal radiation. Motivated by Bekenstein-Smarr differential formula (equation (10)) and First law of thermodynamics (equation (11))¹³:

$$dM = \frac{\kappa_+}{8\pi} dA_+ + \Omega_+ dJ + V_+ dQ \quad (10)$$

$$dU = TdS + \Omega dJ + VdQ \quad (11)$$

By comparing equation (10) with equation (11), the internal energy of the two-dimensional sphere should be equal to the total energy in the sphere. Using equation (7), the internal energy of the two-dimensional sphere can be calculated by using the method of canonical ensemble:

$$U = -\frac{\partial}{\partial\beta} \ln Z = U_0 + 2N \frac{\frac{\hbar\omega'_0}{2}}{e^{\frac{\beta\hbar\omega'_0}{2}} - 1} \quad (12)$$

The second term of the above equation is the thermal motion energy of the system at temperature T, which is equal to the total energy in the sphere.

$$Mc^2 = 2N \frac{\frac{\hbar\omega'_0}{2}}{e^{\frac{\beta\hbar\omega'_0}{2}} - 1} \quad (13)$$

According to equation (2), equation (9) and equation (13), following equation is obtained:

$$\frac{GM}{r^2} = \frac{a_M}{e^{\frac{a_M}{a}} - 1}, \quad a_M = \pi c \omega'_0 \quad (14)$$

When the left and right sides of the equation (14) are multiplied by the mass m, the equation (14) will be written in the following form:

$$\frac{GMm}{r^2} = m \frac{a_M}{e^{\frac{a_M}{a}} - 1} \quad (15)$$

If acceleration a is much larger than a_M , the above equation will be approximated as the following form:

$$\frac{GMm}{r^2} = ma \quad (16)$$

So Newton's second law is the approximate form of the right side of the equation (15). When a is not much larger than a_M , Newton's second law should be revised to the right side of the equation (15). The Unruh effect is used to derive the equation (15), which implies that temperature change of the vacuum leads to the generation of gravity.

3. Application of modified Newton's second law

3.1 Modified Newton's second law and Modified Newtonian Dynamics

In 1983, Milgrom proposed the Modified Newtonian Dynamics¹⁴. He believed that when the gravitational field strength is weak, the Newton's second law should be revised and Newtonian acceleration is not equal to actual acceleration. Modified Newtonian Dynamics can successfully explain some problems of galactic dynamics¹⁵. The relation between the Newtonian acceleration and the actual acceleration is:

$$a_N = a\mu\left(\frac{a}{a_0}\right) \quad (17)$$

$$\text{if } \frac{a}{a_0} \gg 1, \quad \mu\left(\frac{a}{a_0}\right) \rightarrow 1$$

$$\text{if } \frac{a}{a_0} \ll 1, \quad \mu\left(\frac{a}{a_0}\right) \rightarrow \frac{a}{a_0} \quad (18)$$

$\mu(x)$ is a interpolation function, one of the most commonly used form of $\mu(x)$ in Modified Newtonian Dynamics is:

$$\mu(x) = \frac{x}{x+1}$$

Using this form, equation (17) is changed to the following form:

$$a_N = \frac{a^2}{a+a_0} \quad (19)$$

The value of a_0 is approximately equal to $1.2 \times 10^{-10} \text{ m s}^{-2}$. The a_0 of different galaxies are not consistent with each other and it cannot be described by a fundamental constant. These results may

mean that the Modified Newtonian Dynamics is merely an empirical formula rather than a fundamental theory. The Taylor's expansion of the modified acceleration of equation (15) is:

$$a_n = \frac{a^2}{a + \frac{a_M}{2} + \dots} \quad (20)$$

According to equation (8) and equation (14), a_M can be expressed as:

$$a_M = \frac{\pi c^2}{R} \quad (21)$$

In the above equation, the radius of the observable universe R is roughly equivalent to product of the speed of light c and the Hubble constant H_0 . It is easy to find that a_M is also roughly equivalent to $c \times H_0$ and Milgrom also find a_0 is roughly equivalent to $c \times H_0$ in Modified Newtonian Dynamics¹⁵. The radius of the observable universe can be used to estimate the value of a_M , if the R is equal to 46.5 billion light years. $a_M/2$ is approximately equal to $3 \times 10^{-10} \text{ m s}^{-2}$, the value is approximately the same as a_0 , Besides, equation (19) and equation (20) are similar in form. All these results imply Modified Newtonian Dynamics may be an approximate form of modified Newton's second law.

3.2 Modified Newton's second law and Dirac's large numbers hypothesis

In the 1930s, Dirac found that the age of the universe divided by the time it takes light to travel through classical electron radius is approximately 10^{39} . He also found that the ratio of the electrostatic force to the gravitational force between a pair of protons and electrons is also about 10^{39} . Dirac thought that it is not by accident and there should be relationship between the two numbers, which is known as the Dirac's large numbers hypothesis¹⁶. In this section, modified Newton's second law is used to explain the hypothesis.

Considering the gravity between a proton and an electron, following equation is obtained:

$$\frac{GM_p m_e}{r^2} = m_e \frac{a_M}{e^{\frac{a}{a} - 1}} \quad (22)$$

The mass of proton is M_p , electron's mass is m_e . According to equation (14) and equation (8), the following equation is obtained:

$$\frac{R}{r} = \frac{\pi c^2 r}{e^{\frac{aM}{a}-1}} \frac{m_e e^2}{GM_p m_e e^2} \quad (23)$$

Using the expression of the fine structure constant, the above expression can be rewritten into the following form:

$$\frac{R}{r} = \frac{\pi c^2 r}{e^{\frac{aM}{a}-1}} \frac{m_e}{\alpha \hbar} \frac{e^2}{4\pi \epsilon_0 GM_p m_e} \quad (24)$$

In this equation, α is the fine structure constant. It's easy to see that the last term on the right-hand side of the equation (24) is the ratio of the electrostatic force to the gravitational force between a proton and an electron. When r is equal to classical electron radius, the left-hand side of the equation (24) is approximately equal to the ratio of the age of the universe to the time it takes light to travel through the classical electron radius. It seems that there is indeed a relationship between the two numbers. Equation (24) shows that when the other constants in equation (24) are constant, the gravitational constant will increase with time. However, the increase will be extremely slow, which is different from Dirac's conclusion that gravitational constant decreases with time.

3.3 Modified Newton's second law and the measurement of gravitational constant

The Cavendish torsion pendulum experiment can be used to measure the gravitational constant. According to modified Newton's second law, law of the fixed-axis rotation should be revised to following form:

$$M_z = \frac{\frac{aM}{a}}{e^{\frac{aM}{a}-1}} I \beta \quad (23)$$

According to Hooke's law and equation (23), following equation is obtained:

$$\frac{\frac{a_M}{a}}{e^{\frac{a}{a}-1}} \frac{d^2\theta}{dt^2} + \frac{K}{I} \theta = 0 \quad (24)$$

The approximate relationship between the torsion constant K and the vibration period T is described as follows:

$$K = \frac{\frac{a_M}{a}}{e^{\frac{a}{a}-1}} 4\pi^2 \frac{I}{T^2} \quad (25)$$

The expression of the gravitational constant can be obtained from the principle of Cavendish torsion pendulum and equation (25):

$$G = \frac{\frac{a_M}{a}}{e^{\frac{a}{a}-1}} (1 - \beta^2) \frac{\pi^2 d^2 L S}{MT^2 D} \quad (26)$$

In the Cavendish torsion pendulum experiment, M is the mass of the large sphere, d is the distance between the large sphere and the small sphere, L is the distance from the center of the small sphere to the center of the torsion pendulum. S is the displacement of the light point. D is the distance from the torsion pendulum to screen, $1-\beta^2$ is correction term¹⁷.

In fact, the gravitational constant measured in the experiment is G_1 rather gravitational constant G , The relationship between them is as follows:

$$G_1 = \frac{e^{\frac{a}{a}-1}}{\frac{a_M}{a}} G = (1 - \beta^2) \frac{\pi^2 d^2 L S}{MT^2 D} \quad (27)$$

Here G_1 is related to acceleration. In order to verify the relationship between G and G_1 in equation (27), results from high-precision experiments published over the last twenty years are adopted. These experiments were conducted by the groups of Quinn *et al* ($6.67515 \times 10^{-11} \text{ m}^3 \text{ kg}^{-1} \text{ s}^{-2}$), Gundlach and Merkowitz ($6.674215 \times 10^{-11} \text{ m}^3 \text{ kg}^{-1} \text{ s}^{-2}$), Li *et al* ($6.674484 \times 10^{-11} \text{ m}^3 \text{ kg}^{-1} \text{ s}^{-2}$), Schlamminger *et al* ($6.674252 \times 10^{-11} \text{ m}^3 \text{ kg}^{-1} \text{ s}^{-2}$) and Newman *et al* ($6.67433 \times 10^{-11} \text{ m}^3 \text{ kg}^{-1} \text{ s}^{-2}$). Acceleration, the measurement result and error of each experiment are given in references [18]. Fitting result is shown in FIG. 1, the result shows that modified Newton's second law can fit these experimental results very

successfully. It means that modified Newton's second law can explain the problem that the measurement results of different experimental groups are inconsistent within the error range. More high-precision torsion pendulum experiments can be used to test the modified Newton's second law in the future.

FIG. 1: Fitting graph. Different groups measure the gravitational constant with different method. AAF: angular acceleration feedback. ToS: time of swing. ESS: electrostatic servo. G and a_M are fitting parameters. The fitting value of G is $6.6742 \times 10^{-11} \text{ m}^3 \text{ kg}^{-1} \text{ s}^{-2}$, The fitting value of a_M is $1.3111 \times 10^{-11} \text{ m}^2 \text{ s}^{-2}$.

4. SUMMARY AND DISCUSSION

In this paper, event horizon of black hole is treated as an interacting particle system. It is easy to get the expression for entropy of a black hole. The hypothesis is extended to any two-dimensional sphere.

And the internal energy of the two-dimensional sphere is considered equal to the total energy in the sphere. Under these assumptions, modified Newton's second law and universal gravitation formula can be obtained. By comparing Modified Newtonian Dynamics with modified Newton's second law, the first two terms of the Taylor expansion of the modified Newton's second law are consistent with Modified Newtonian Dynamics and the value of $a_M/2$ is approximately equal to a_0 , it is considered that Modified Newtonian Dynamics may be an approximate form of modified Newton's second law. Using the modified Newton's second law, It is found that modified Newton's second law can explain the Dirac's large numbers hypothesis and this paper believes that the gravitational constant increases extremely slowly over time. The modified Newton's second law is also applied to the problem that some measurement results of different experimental groups are inconsistent within the error range, it is pointed out that the gravitational constant measured by the present method is not a fixed value, the measured value of the gravitational constant is related to acceleration. The fitting results agrees very well with the experimental data of different experimental groups. It means that the modified Newton's second is very successful in explaining the inconsistencies in measurements of the gravitational constant.

ω_i in equation (6) is discontinuous, which leads to that Newton's second law needs to be modified when the acceleration is weak. If a_N is equal to a_n , according to equation (19) and equation (20) the value of $a_M/2$ should be smaller than a_0 . However, a_0 in Modified Newtonian Dynamics and a_M in modified Newton's second law are only in the same order of magnitude and $a_M/2$ is several times larger than a_0 . One of the possible reasons is that the modified Newton's second will lead to a revision of Friedman's equations and general relativity. If Friedman's equations and general relativity are modified, the radius of the observable universe may be different from the result of our current theoretical calculations.

Another possible reason is that standing wave condition in equation (6) may need to be modified to obtain a more accurate value of a_0 , these questions are in need of further study.

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